

Observing Human Behaviors in an Interactive Art Installation¹

Takashi Kiriya - Graduate School of Film and New Media, Tokyo University of the Arts, Yokohama, Japan, kiriyama@gsfnm.jp

Masahiko Sato - Graduate School of Film and New Media, Tokyo University of the Arts, Yokohama, Japan, sato@gsfnm.jp

Abstract

Arithmetik Garden is an interactive art installation to perform arithmetic by going through gates. By analyzing routes created by viewers, we found differences between human behaviors and computer-generated optimal solutions. We also discovered that the viewer's emotional change could be detected by monitoring human behaviors.

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Introduction

Arithmetik Garden is an interactive installation designed to provide the viewer with an experience of performing arithmetic by using the body. This installation consists of eight gates, including an entrance gate, an exit gate shown as $= 73$, and six arithmetic gates shown as $+5$, $+8$, $\times 3$, $\times 7$, -4 , and $\div 2$. The eight gates of 240cm in height by 125cm in width stand in a square area of 10m by 10m (Figure 1). There are ten cards with different initial numbers -8, -1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 36, 87, and 91 (Figure 2). The viewer picks up a card at the entrance and hangs it around the neck. Then the viewer makes the initial number equal to the goal number 73 by going through the six arithmetic gates any times in any order. For instance, if the viewer starts with 4 and then goes through the $+8$ gate, the number is now $4 + 8 = 12$. If the viewer further goes to the $\times 3$ gate, the number will be $(4 + 8) \times 3 = 36$. The $\div 2$ gate works only with even numbers, such as $(4 + 8) \times 3 \div 2 = 18$.

Figure 1: Arithmetik Garden.²

Figure 2: Cards with initial numbers.

² Photo by Keizo Kioku, Courtesy of Mori Art Museum

Starting from 7, for instance, one can take a route

$$7 \xrightarrow{\times 7} 49 \xrightarrow{+5} 54 \xrightarrow{-4} 50 \xrightarrow{\times 3} 150 \xrightarrow{-4} 146 \xrightarrow{\div 2} 73$$

to arrive at the goal 73. Here, $N \xrightarrow{op} M$ means that by going through the *op* gate the current number changes from *N* to *M*. If the viewer becomes uncertain about the number, he or she can go to the equation monitor in the corner (Figure 3). It displays the route taken so far as an equation such as

$$((7 \times 7 + 5 - 4) \times 3 - 4) \div 2 = 73.$$

Figure 3: Equation monitor.

The Arithmetik Garden had been exhibited at the Mori Art Museum in Tokyo from Oct 13, 2007 to Jan 14, 2008 (Mori 2007). Over the three-month period of exhibition, a total of 43,156 viewers experienced this exhibit. During the exhibition, we observed how viewers interacted with this installation. In the rest of this paper, we discuss the design of the Arithmetik Garden and findings from the observation.

System Design

The Arithmetik Garden employs RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) technology. The RFID readers inside the eight gates wirelessly communicate with ID tags embedded in the number cards. When one of the readers detects a tag, it sends the tag's ID to the server via a network (Figure 4). The event is stored in an SQL server along with the tag's ID, the operation of the gate, and the time of event. The entrance gate resets the route associated with the card. The exit gate displays O or X by comparing the current number and the goal number 73.

Figure 4: System layout.

The technology behind the Arithmetik Garden is completely hidden from the user. People walk in the installation without worrying about menus and buttons. In fact, they do not touch anything from the entrance to the exit, because all sensing is done wirelessly by the RFID readers.

From outside the installation, one can watch people inside doing arithmetic. Watching people is engaging as their movements reflect their thoughts.

A state diagram of the Arithmetik Garden is shown in Figure 5. The nodes and links represent current numbers and transitions between them. The diagram contains;

- the goal number 73,
- numbers within distance 4 to the goal,
- links between numbers within distance 3 to the goal,
- initial numbers -8, -1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 36, 87, and 91, and
- other numbers and links on the shortest routes from the initial numbers to the goal.

Here, distance d to 73 means that it takes at least d steps to arrive at 73. For instance,

$$2 \xrightarrow{\times 3} 6 \xrightarrow{+5} 11 \xrightarrow{\times 7} 77 \xrightarrow{-4} 73$$

is the shortest route from 2 to 73, so 2 is of distance 4 to 73.

A printed version of the state diagram is posted on the wall near the exit gate. It allows the viewer to reflect on the route he or she took. The diagram motivates people to take other routes and different initial numbers in the next trial.

Observing Human Behaviors

During exhibition of the Arithmetik Garden, we collected records of routes taken by viewers. A record includes an initial number, a sequence of arithmetic operations, and timestamps of passing through gates. The records are exported from the SQL server and transformed into an XML format. We used XQuery and XSLT for data analysis, because they are convenient to look for patterns in a large amount of data (Kiryama 2007).

By examining data, we found that people did not always take the shortest routes. For instance, if the current number is 10, there are two shortest routes to the goal;

$$10 \xrightarrow{+5} 15 \xrightarrow{-4} 11 \xrightarrow{\times 7} 77 \xrightarrow{-4} 73, \text{ and}$$

$$10 \xrightarrow{-4} 6 \xrightarrow{+5} 11 \xrightarrow{\times 7} 77 \xrightarrow{-4} 73.$$

But among 2,141 cases in which the current number became 10, 1,098 times people chose to go to $\times 7$ next. We suppose that $\times 7$ appears to be most promising, as $\times 7$ produces 70, which is numerically close to 73. But, in fact, 70 is six steps away from 73 and going through $\times 7$ is moving away from the goal. As shown in Figure 6, there were more cases (1,098) in which people went to $\times 7$ than the total number of cases in which people went to $\times 7$ (339) and -4 (171).

Table 1 shows average time spent to choose the next gate after the current number 10. It took 15.9 seconds in average to decide to go through $\times 7$, which was the shortest among other choices. It suggests that the largest number of people choose the $\times 7$ gate by their intuition.

Figure 6: Routes from 10.

Table 1: Transitions from 10 and average time before making the transitions.

Current number	Gate	Transition	Number of cases	Average time (seconds)
10	$\times 7$	$10 \xrightarrow{\times 7} 70$	1,098	15.9
	$+5$	$10 \xrightarrow{+5} 15$	339	18.2
	$+8$	$10 \xrightarrow{+8} 18$	121	21.2
	$\times 3$	$10 \xrightarrow{\times 3} 30$	169	22.0
	-4	$10 \xrightarrow{-4} 6$	289	24.4
	$\div 2$	$10 \xrightarrow{\div 2} 5$	121	34.6

Another interesting behavior we found in data is absorption in an immediate goal. People sometimes try to achieve a goal at hand without looking for a better alternative. For instance, when the current number is 65, going through the +8 gate will make the number 73. Of a total of 3,980 cases in which the current number became 65, 3,408 times people actually went to the +8 gate to reach the goal. Among the rest of them, 437 times (11% of the total 3,980 cases), people went to the +5 gate instead. Since the +8 and +5 gates are located in the same distance to the goal, choosing +5 over +8 cannot be attributed to the physical layout. We further studied the 437 cases of taking the +5 gate. In 236 cases of them (54% of the total 437), people went through the +5 gate twice as in

$$60 \xrightarrow{+5} 65 \xrightarrow{+5} 70.$$

In 115 cases (26% of the total 437), they went through the +5 gate three times in a row as in

$$60 \xrightarrow{+5} 65 \xrightarrow{+5} 70 \xrightarrow{+5} 75.$$

This pattern of going through the +5 gate multiple times near the goal seems that people wanted to increase the current number by going through the +5 gate. Once people started to do it, they tend to forget about looking for alternatives.

By comparing optimal routes with actual records created by people, we can discover gaps between logical optimality and human decision making. We can take advantage of this finding to make the installation more challenging.

Emotional Aspects

Before the exhibition of the Arithmetik Garden, we conducted a public testing at university. We videotaped 340 people in the public testing and analyzed how they reacted to the situation. By watching video, we found that people started to run near the end of the route because they were now confident about the rest of their routes. It is also found in data that the intervals from a gate to the next became shorter near the end of route. For some viewers a sudden change of facial expression emerges. We located such a moment of change in data and reviewed the video of that moment. The video recording indicated that people were indeed delighted at knowing how to reach the goal. We believe that by monitoring data we can detect a moment of emotional change in interactive art installation. It may be useful for making the system respond to emotional changes of the viewer (Norman 2004).

Although the minimum distance from the initial numbers to the goal is 4 steps, typically people spend 8 to 12 steps to reach the goal. It is not only because doing arithmetic in mind is difficult. We think that people need to understand the nature of the question by exploring the space. Once the rules became clear, they can focus on the planning of their routes. If it is true, there may be another clue of detecting an emotional change from exploration to concentration by looking at the pattern of selecting gates.

Conclusions

For understanding human behaviors in the Arithmetik Garden, it was extremely useful to keep track all records of interactions. We found in the records that the routes taken by human are different from computer-generated optimal solutions. People tend to select a seemingly promising route such as $10 \xrightarrow{\times 7} 70$ over optimal choices $10 \xrightarrow{+5} 15$ and $10 \xrightarrow{-4} 6$. The fact that people spent less time for the transition $10 \xrightarrow{\times 7} 70$ than any other alternatives indicates that it was made intuitively. Another finding is that people tend to stick an immediate goal that they created. While increasing the current number to 73 by going through the +5 gate multiple times, people tend to miss a solution such as $60 \xrightarrow{+5} 65 \xrightarrow{\times 8} 73$. It was also found that people started to run when they became confident about the rest of the route. Such a change can be detected by monitoring intervals between gates. Monitoring the user behavior will be useful to design an interactive system that responds to a change of user's emotion.

Future research includes applying the data analysis techniques employed in this research to other interactive art installations to extend understanding about human behaviors.

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References

- Mori Art Museum (2007). “Roppongi Crossing 2007: Future Beats in Japanese Contemporary Art”.
- Kiriyama, T. (2007). “Representing User Interaction Data of the Arithmetik Garden”. Asian Topic Maps Summit 2007.
- Norman, D.A. (2004). Emotional Design, Basic Books.